

phenotypic score of 1; short and low-tillering varieties were scored 7.

At Banaue, 2 plants/entry were sampled to measure the characters under study; 1 plant/entry was sampled at Chuncheon. Correlation between and among the characters measured is shown in the figure. Root dry weight was considered an indicator of good rooting ability in low-temperature conditions.

Scores on phenotypic vigor of plants — scored on a 1-9 scale — were negatively correlated with other characters. A significant correlation between root dry weight and tiller number indicated

possible selection of plants that have good rooting ability on the basis of tiller number in low temperatures. This would eliminate the tedious work of carefully pulling the seedlings and washing the soil off the roots. Root length contributed much toward root dry weight, and a positive significant correlation between seedling height and root length revealed an indirect effect of seedling height on root dry weight. Tiller number, however, had no effect on root length at Banaue. In Chuncheon, Korea, phenotypic vigor was significantly correlated with root length and root dry weight, but not with tiller

number. Tiller number was significantly correlated with root dry weight, as in Banaue. But unlike in Banaue, the seedling height was significantly correlated with root dry weight — perhaps because the Banaue observation was taken at a later growth stage.

Results in Banaue and Chuncheon indicate that selection for plants with good tillering ability in low-temperature conditions will also select plants with good rooting ability. The early establishment of transplanted seedlings is important in low-temperature areas, which generally have short growing seasons. ■

Use of small pots for testing cold tolerance of crosses at seedling and flowering stages under rapid generation advance

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The rapid generation advance (RGA) program at IRRI generally uses small plastic square pots (5.5 × 5.5 × 5.0 cm). The practicality of these pots for screening or breeding during RGA was tested. Selection for low temperature tolerance was done at two plant stages: seedling and flowering. Selection at those stages is important in screening donor parents for cold tolerance crossing. The table shows the performance of seven cold tolerance crosses in small pots.

The F₂ seedlings were screened in a cold water tank at 12° C. Thirty percent of the seedlings were found tolerant of low temperature. The susceptible plants were discarded and the tolerant plants were grown under normal water temperatures.

During the flowering stage, the plants were placed in a dark room at 15° C for 3 days, and then taken back to the greenhouse (maximum temperature less than 30° C). The percentage of sterility was taken at harvest time and used as a criterion for selection. Plants with less than 30% sterility were selected.

The use of small square pots for cold tolerance screening at flowering was compared with that of the standard 4-liter pots. A set of 28 varieties were

Selection efficiency for 7 cold-tolerant crosses grown in small pots during the F₂. IRRI, 1980.

Cross	F ₂ seeds (no.) (A)	No. selected after screening			Selection efficiency (%)		
		At seedling stage (B)	At flowering stage (C)	efficiency (%)			
				B/A	C/A	C/B	
Silewah/IR3880-13	872	180	27	21	3	15	
IR3841-14-2-2-3/IET2815	849	235	73	28	9	31	
IET2815/IR6172-6-3	123	41	18	33	2	5	
iET2845/CRP6-1899-25/Cul. 854	444	145	53	33	12	37	
Taipei NO 309, B922c-Mr-91	114	60	14	53	12	23	
Taipei NO 309/IR26	500	272	21	54	4	8	
Dumsiah 81/RNR 7303	113	111	0	98	0	0	

planted in both pots. The results showed a highly significant correlation ($t = .7095^{**}$) indicating that the small pots can be used in screening for cold tolerance at flowering.

The study shows that during screening of low-temperature crosses, small pots are best used at the seedling and flowering stages. Their use will reduce the growth duration by 10 to 20 days (to an av of 90 days), plant height by 10 to 20 cm (to an av of 75 cm), and spikelet number by 20 spikelets/plant (to an av of 50). The reduction in spikelet number will not affect the breeding process, and

the shorter growth duration will hasten the breeding program. Use of small pots will involve the following steps:

1. Mix fine soil and fertilizer uniformly.
2. Use pregerminated seeds at 2 seeds/pot and thin out weak seedlings.
3. Place pots on pallets with plastic lining.
4. Supply adequate water to prevent the plants from drying.
5. There should be at least 2,000 plants for F₂ crosses. ■

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Preliminary studies on isolation and means of spread of the rice leaf scald fungus in Sierra Leone

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The incidence of leaf scald disease of rice caused by the fungus *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has increased in the past 4 years in Sierra Leone. Therefore, work was initiated to develop a technique to rapidly inoculate and screen for leaf